

Sphinx Head Triangulation Points

Label
16viii2

POINT	DESCRIPTION	PAGE 1 OF 4
1	TOP N LAPPET NEMES, TOP LINE HEAD (VERY SLIGHT BUMP AT POINT)	
2	" " " " CEMENT(?) RECESS BRIDGING TO CAP LINE	
3	CEMENT BUMP MEETS END OF CAP, BACK N SIDE, HEAD TOP LINE	
4	INFLECTION POINT (TURN OF CAP), N SIDE, HEAD TOP LINE, SMALL RAISED BUMP	
5	N SIDE, RAISED PORTION, JUST N OF COBRA (SMALL NODULE) TOP HEAD LINE	
6	N SIDE COBRA, AGAINST CAP, TOP HEAD LINE	
7	N SIDE, CENTER PART COBRA, HEAD TOP LINE	
8	S SIDE CENTER PART COBRA, HEAD TOP LINE	
9	S SIDE COBRA (AT INFLECTION, TIP NODULE OF BREAK, RAISED PART (NOT AGAINST CAP PLANE) (AS OPP TO 6)	
10	S SIDE COBRA (AGAINST CAP) (Center first pleat from cobra → S) ↳ From NE → SW Perspective HEAD TOP LINE	
11	S SIDE, 5th PLEAT FROM COBRA → S, S SIDE PLEAT (WIDE PLEAT) APPRX. INFLECTION POINT, TOP LINE HEAD.	
12	INFLECTION CURVE POINT, S SIDE, TOP LINE HEAD, BACK TOWARD NEMES FOLD, N SIDE 2nd PLEAT FROM FOLD LINE → N	
13	FOLD JOINT, S SIDE, TOP LINE HEAD (AT S EDGE 1ST PLEAT FROM FOLD → N	
14	TOP S LAPPET OF NEMES (JUST SLIGHTLY LOWER THAN TOP LINE HEAD	
15	N SIDE, MEETING CHEEK AND EAR (FARTHEST EXT. CHEEK TO → N " ")	
16	N SIDE OF N EAR, FARTHEST → N EXT.	
17	N SIDE LOWER LAPPET NEMES, FARTHEST EXT. → N (JUNCT. MOD CEMENT AND B.R.)	
18	N SIDE, NOSE AREA, BEGINNING OF CHEEK SHALEY UNIT AT DEEP CREVASS SECTION	
19	N SIDE, CHEEK, END OF WEATHERED BAND, FRONT CHEEK (ALIGN TO RECTANGULAR WEATHERED-HOLE	
20	END OF SHALEY WEATHERED SECTION, N SIDE, APPRX. INFLECTION CHEEK	
21	BEGINNING OF SHALEY WEATHERED SECTION, N SIDE UPPER LIP (PROTRUDING PORTION, S END OF WEATHERED SECTION	
22	APPRX. CENTER, RAISED PORTION UPPER LIP (S SIDE RAISED (ORIGINAL) PART UPPER LIP, AT BREAK (FORWARD)	
23	S SIDE UPPER LIP (DAMAGED) ABOVE LIP CENTER LINE, AT CORAL-LIKE HOLE	
24	N END MOUTH LINE (SCANT TRACES)	

25. S END MOUTH LINE
26. S SIDE CHEEK, UPPER SHALEY UNIT, S SIDE OF SMALL ORB LONG WEATHERED PATCH
27. S SIDE CHEEK, UPPER SHALEY UNIT, S SIDE DARK STREAK DOWN FACE - ITS INTERSECTION W. UPPER SHALEY UNIT.
28. S SIDE, MEETING OF CHEEK AND EAR (FARTHEST EXT. CHEEK → ^N S)
29. S SIDE S EAR (FARTHEST EXT. → S) AGAINST LAPPET
30. LOWER END S SIDE LAPPET, E FACE, REMAINS ORIGINAL PLEATED SURFACE
BEHIND/ABOVE CEMENT HUMPS AT JUNCTURE
31. N SIDE, MEETING OF NECK AND LOWER LINE LAPPET
32. S SIDE, MEETING OF NECK AND LOWER LINE LAPPET (LOWEST IRREGULAR LINE BELOW MOD. CEMENT PLEAT FILL)
33. NE CORNER BED 7ii (N SHOULDER) SMALL NODULE - SIGHT
34. SE CORNER BED 7i-7ii (S SHOULDER) SIGHT NODULE ON FACE
35. S SIDE BOTTOM COBRA-CAP LINE
36. N SIDE BOTTOM COBRA-CAP LINE
37. S END S EYE BROW
38. HIGH (INFLECTION) POINT S EYE BROW (ALIGN W/ N SIDE BREAKAGE ON UNDERSIDE END)
39. N SIDE, S EYEBROW
40. S END, N EYEBROW
41. HIGH (INFLECTION) POINT N EYEBROW (SIGHT SMALL ^{HOLE - N SIDE} ABOVE N END THIN CRACK)
42. N END, N EYEBROW (AT BEGINNING OF PAINTED BAND)
43. BREAK AT BRIDGE OF NOSE (CENTER - SIGHT LARGE WHITE SPOT INSIDE BREAK)
44. S SIDE TOP OF S EAR (JOIN W. NEMES)
45. N SIDE TOP OF ^S EAR (JOIN W/ HEAD)
46. S SIDE (END) S EYE SOCKET
47. N SIDE (END) S EYE SOCKET
48. S SIDE (END) N EYE SOCKET
49. N END N EYE SOCKET
50. S SIDE TOP (JOIN W/ HEAD) N. EAR
51. N SIDE TOP (JOIN W/ NEMES) N EAR

S. SIDE,

52. N END CHEEK BRIDGE (NEAR NOSE BREAK) (SIGHT S END OF BREAK)

N. SIDE

53. S END CHEEK BRIDGE (NEAR - AT NOSE BREAK (SIGHT OUTSIDE EDGE OF BREAK)

54. INFLECTION POINT CHIN - S SIDE (SIGHT ^S EDGE OF PATCH OF SMOOTH ORIGINAL SURFACE

55. N INFLECTION POINT OF CHIN (SIGHT S EDGE WHITE PATCH ON UNDERSIDE

E SIDE

56. LOWER LINE, N SIDE NEMES, RECTANGULAR SECTION JUTTING OUT JUST AROUND N CORNER

57. NEMES BOTTOM LINE, N SIDE, W EDGE RECTANGULAR SECTION JUTTING OUT JUST AROUND N CORNER

58. PLANNING POINT ON S SIDE CHEST ON CORNER BED SII

59. " " BOSS CENTER " "

60. " " N SIDE CHEST CORNER " "

61. S SIDE CORNER BED 8 (SE CORNER) PROTRUDING KNDS

NOTE NE CORNER BED 8 ALMOST RIGHT AT BOTTOM CEMENT SUPPORT OF LAPPETS

62. BOTTOM LAPPETS SUPPORT - N SIDE

63. " " " - S SIDE

64. LOWER CHIN LINE, JUST S OF CENTER, SIGHT BORDER BETWEEN POCKETED PATCH, SMOOTH PATCH ON FACE OF CHIN

65. S CORNER LOWER LAPPET NEMES W-MOST EDGE, SIGHT EDGE OF ORIGINAL SURFACE

66. TRUE CORNER EDGE LOWER S. LAPPET - JUST ABOVE PTS. 30, 65

67. S SIDE LOWER NEMES LINE, INWARD INFLECTION SIGHT

68. S SIDE LOWER NEMES LINE, OUTWARD INFLECTION SIGHT

69. S SIDE REAR BREAK NEMES TAIL

70. HEAD, TOP, N SIDE - CUT BACK WEST OF TOP NEMES LAPPET

71. HEAD TOP N SIDE LINE OF CEMENT FILL, BED ROCK GAP

72. NEMES TAIL BREAK N SIDE

73. TOP HEAD LINE, BACK BUMP, S SIDE

74. " " " " " N SIDE